

FAIR Principles for Training Resources

Group 2 - Accessible

Version 1.0

Introduction

Once the learner/trainee finds the required content, they need to be able to access and “use” it. **What does it mean for the training content to be accessible?** The FAIR Data and Software Principles [2,3] focus on making data, software and related metadata ‘retrievable via standardised protocols’. Similarly, the “Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR” [1] only have one rule related to accessibility:

- **Define access rules for your training materials**

How do you interpret the above rule? What should be included in those access rules? Are there any other characteristics of the training content that affect its accessibility? The general FAIR principles also state the metadata should be accessible, even if the data are no longer available (principle A2). Should it be applied to training resources? How?

In this session we would like you to think about and discuss what it means for the training content to be accessible, and following the instructions included below, formulate a list of specific recommendations for making HPC/RCD/RSE training content more **Accessible**.

Fig 1. Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR. The first rule—to share—is the central starting point; the Findability rules include description, identity, and registration; the latter two, together with access rules, correspond to Accessibility; Interoperability stands on its own, with one rule about formats; the remaining four rules cover different aspects of Reusability. Illustration from Luc Wiegiers and Celia van Gelder: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3593257>.

Instructions

The session is split into 3 parts:

- Group discussion (25min)
- Report out recommendations (10min)
- Contribute recommendations to the Best Practices Guide (15min)

Part 1 - Group Discussion:

Please think about and discuss these points:

Notetaker: keep notes in the template below.

- Define your term - **Accessible** - what does it mean in the context of training content?
- How can we evaluate 'accessibility' of the existing content?
- How can we make content that is **Accessible**? List as many approaches/implementation options as you can think of given, for example:
 - Size of the training repository
 - Types of material
 - Delivery method
 - Audiences

Part 2 - Report out recommendations

Notetaker: keep notes in the template below.

Synthesize your discussion into best practices recommendations for report out:

- Focus on the 3 points that were most important to your group (that you found most compelling, interesting, controversial)

Part 3 - Contribute recommendations to the Best Practices Guide

Starting with your top three recommendations, please edit and expand on your recommendations and add them to [here](#). If you run out of time during this session, or you are interested in building the [Best Practices Guide](#) you can continue to add content until **1 August 2025**.

Please try to include recommendations for both new and existing training content, keeping in mind the below:

- Different types of content
- Who is the content being FAIRified for?
- What resources or capabilities are needed?
- Are there institutional or regulatory considerations?

Participants

Please assign the following roles in your group to make the most of the available time, including **name, affiliation and email addresses** (for anyone wishing to be involved in the further efforts).

Facilitator:

Note taker:

Reporter:

Team:

Group Discussion Notes

Please try to capture your discussion here:

Add your notes here

Group Recommendations

Please write down your recommendations for making the training resources more **Accessible**:

Add your recommendations here

Content to be added to the Best Practices Guide

The below content will be refined and added to the content FAIRfying Best Practice Guide. Please try to include recommendations for the following three categories:

- **Evaluating Accessibility**
- **How to create Accessible resources**
- **How to improve Accessibility of existing content**

Add your content here

References:

- [1] Garcia L, Batut B, Burke ML, Kuzak M, Psomopoulos F, Arcila R, et al. (2020) Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR. PLoS Comput Biol 16(5): e1007854. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007854>
- [2] <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>
- [3] Barker, M., Chue Hong, N.P., Katz, D.S. *et al.* Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software. *Sci Data* 9, 622 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>